

Design for human flourishing in architecture: Programmatic writing as a way to design socio-cultural affordances

Ruth Stevens¹

ruth.stevens@uhasselt.be

Ann Petermans¹

ann.petermans@uhasselt.be

Jan Vanrie¹

jan.vanrie@uhasselt.be

¹Hasselt University,
Belgium

Abstract In architectural design for human flourishing (DfHF), compatibility between the environment and the user is crucial. A supportive relationship between the two is characterized by the environment's action possibilities and the user's perception thereof in terms of complementarity with the users' psychological needs and personal goals.

This paper highlights a design method called "programmatic writing", that was developed in a student design project. Programmatic writing connects target groups' needs and an enriched program within an architectural design, by applying techniques as narratives and scenario writing. This is a first crucial step in an architectural DfHF-process.

In this paper, first, a short theoretical background of DfHF and the set-up of the design project are sketched. Next, the development of the design method is discussed through an analysis of the design process in the exercise. Hereby, we aim to contribute to the development of an architectural DfHF-process.

Keywords *Architecture, Design for human flourishing, Design exercise, Programmatic writing, Affordances*

Introduction

Human flourishing is a topic in design research that is starting to receive attention today (e.g. Desmet & Pohlmeier, 2013), but in the field of architecture, it remains rather underexposed (e.g. Delle Fave et al, 2011; Stevens et al, 2014, 2016a). As a design approach, design for human flourishing (DfHF) consequently could benefit from a theoretical basis that can be used to develop practical tools for architects to guide them to adopt this approach. In that respect, this paper discusses the development of the design method of "programmatic writing", with the purpose of introducing it as a possible method to be applied in an architectural DfHF-process.

A trajectory to design for human flourishing: designing spatial flourishing affordances

Recently, we have proposed a theoretical trajectory to design architecture for human flourishing, see Figure 1 (Stevens et al, 2016a). It takes an affordance-approach and is based on a re-interpretation of the Vitruvian architectural quality criterion of *Venustas*, that comprises the poetic, experiential properties of architecture, to anchor it in architectural theory. For the development of the theoretical trajectory, affordance theories -starting from the basic work of Gibson (1979), over Warren (1984), Norman (2002), Chemero (2003, 2009) and Rietveld and Kiverstein (2014)- are researched by the first author (a designer) from a humane angle, in order to capture what benefits an environmental affordance provides to its users, more particularly in terms of compliance with

users' needs. We noticed that over time, the affordance evolved from only responding to basic, instinctive and physical needs, towards including more cultural and psychological user characteristics. Our study on affordance theories concluded with introducing 'spatial flourishing affordances', a new, complete humane outlook on affordances. Spatial flourishing affordances can be defined as an environmental affordance that invites, incites and enthuses the user to undertake activities that the environment enables, in order to fulfil their psychological needs and personal goals. In that way, a person can be set on its way to flourishing (Stevens et al, 2016a). The trajectory is comprised of three main components that need to be treated by architects in a specific order. As Figure 1 demonstrates, first, the architect must invest in his 'target group', and collect psychological information regarding their needs, goals and daily goings. Next, these data need to be processed into an elaborate programming phase in which activities need to be designed, complying with the expectations, and psychological and socio-cultural needs and wants of the target group. Finally, the program needs to be translated into a material design, via architectural elements.

In DfHF, the responsibility of architects lies in creating architectural conditions under which a specific target group can flourish; in designing spaces that psychologically support, invite, enthuse and enable users to undertake meaningful actions, and thereby empower themselves and gain a positive effect

Figure 1. A theoretical trajectory to DfHF in architecture: designing spatial flourishing affordances.

on their flourishing. Note that this trajectory is not yet a design methodology. It provides architects with a general frame of reference to give direction to their architectural process, and assists them in practicing a new, more humane way of architectural thinking. This paper however is a first step in concretizing the trajectory. Through designerly and empirically exploring this proposed trajectory, we aim to distil useful and more concrete applicable information for architects, and formulate how they can work with the components in practice.

In the next chapters, we will describe the student design project “Layer Cake”, in which we aimed to create flourishing architecture for elderly persons by empathically designing social environments as seen *through their eyes*. We will analyse the design process with the use of Figure 1, the theoretical trajectory for human flourishing. Concretely, we will zoom in on the design of the ‘socio-cultural affordances’ that are created via the first two trajectory-components, that is, ‘target group’ and ‘program’ (visualized in the highlighted left part of Figure 1). Next, we discuss the development of the design method of programmatic writing that evolved from unravelling the design steps that students took in working with ‘target group’ and ‘program’. To conclude, we propose programmatic writing as a design method that architects can apply in order to create socio-cultural affordances and by that, take concrete measures to DfHF.

Design studio project “Layer Cake”

Layer Cake was a two-week fulltime master class in architectural DfHF, organized in February 2014. The task was to design social programs for a high-rise residential building for people over 60 years, comprised of 40 residential floors (containing private apartments, service flats or even care rooms) interlarded with 10 ‘public floors’ with a variety in social programs, see Figure 2. The ten public floor designs formed the design exercise, and needed to (1) assist residents in flourishing, (2) address the entire group of residents, differing in physical and other age-related characteristics, and (3) root the building socially in the neighbouring urban fabric. The design

brief had an overarching humane character; neither further programmatic demands nor spatial end terms were formulated. The exercise focused on the experiential character of spaces. Ten design groups were each comprised of four master students in interior architecture, and each group was attributed one public floor of the high-rise living tower to configure into a ‘social layer’ meeting the humane design brief.

Designing socio-cultural affordances, tested in Layer Cake

In the exercise Layer Cake, students were obliged to spend the first design week entirely on their ‘social concept’, by which we mean they had to select a basic social function for their floor, developing it further into a number of meaningful activities and experiences that fit the needs of the target group. Communication of these intangible design results was also an important factor. Altogether, the designing of these so-called ‘socio-cultural affordances’ formed the centre of gravity of the exercise. Only in the second week we asked students to make an actual spatial translation, by 3D modelling, and thereby transforming the program into an architectural 3D design. In this paper, we will only discuss the first design week, namely designing the ‘social concept’, in which the design method of programmatic writing was developed. In terms of the trajectory, this implies working with the design components ‘target group’ and ‘program’, as visualized in the highlighted left part of Figure 1.

Below, we will explain the development of the design method programmatic writing, by unravelling the students’ design process per component of the trajectory. More in detail, per component we first present short theoretical insights that were valuable and applicable to incorporate in the design process. Secondly, we present how these insights were inserted in the set-up of the design exercise. Thirdly, we discuss in what way the students received and handled these insights in the actual design process.

The ten design projects in Layer Cake:

1. Jong geleerd oud gedaan
2. Ex Libris
3. Marktforum
4. Grootmoeders keuken
5. Sport-o-rama
6. Tussen de soep en de patatten
7. Spotted
8. Herinnering als vorm van ontplooiing
9. Theater in het park
10. Een (her)beleving

Figure 2. Layer Cake: a photo of the scale model, a sketch of the tower and a list of the ten designed projects that came out of the exercise.

Component one Target group: defining target group specifics

Theory

To empathically connect with their target group, architects need specific experiential information: daily goings, hopes and fears, aspirations, etcetera. Architects have at least two options in gathering this kind of psychological information: collect data themselves, or consult academic sociological data regarding the target group.

In the first option of gathering information themselves, many methods come to mind. Architects that design small projects for a single client, for instance living spaces, are familiar with asking clients for their daily routines, or they build on their own intuition or predicate upon personal 'living' experiences to empathize with clients. This is what Juhani Pallasmaa refers to when stating: *"The only proper way to deal with the everyday practice of architecture is that the architect becomes the client him- or herself"* (Havik & Tielens, 2013, p. 41). However, when the 'client' is not a single family requesting a design for a house, but a varied audience in a (semi-) public building such as residential care, architects needs to tap into other approaches, since empathizing with a more abstract and undefined client does not come natural. Additionally, architects in formation are barely confronted with psychological and social sciences (e.g. Oppliger, 2015), which impedes the interpretation of socio-cultural knowledge and its inclusion in a spatial design process.

With Layer Cake, we attempted to overcome this burden for architects, by applying techniques from narrative theory and thereby integrating the user into the design process, not as a co-designer but as a sort of narrator. Parnell (2003) already argued that listening to clients and communicating with people from day one in the design process, can help architecture students to see their perspective on design and value them within the design, and Till (2005) recognizes the power of simple, ordinary conversations in search for new methods of communication with clients in design. Gerards and De Bleeckere (2014) have already successfully brought these insights into a design exercise with architecture

students, and developed narrative thinking as an anchor throughout the design process and a help to connect designers and users. In this respect, narratives show potential to get to know future users and make an empathic connection. We believe narratives contribute to profiling and personifying unknown clients, which in DfHF can help architects to make more empathized design decisions. DfHF is designing meaningful activities that are in accordance with the users' psychological needs and personal goals; personal narratives linked to the users as such, can be viewed as a valuable tool to set designers on a path to designerly thinking in terms of activities and usage patterns, rooted in the living environment of the user. This could lead to more daring and creative design solutions. We thereby felt that narratives are a suitable method to be included in the design process of component one, 'target group', in the exercise.

In the second option, namely that architects would apply data from scientific research, they often struggle with the format under which data are presented; these are often written in a language that architects are not acquainted with and this kind of knowledge is not directly applicable in design processes. However, implementing research data can assist designers in fulfilling their humane task, but only when the research is directed at and serving to the architect's work. As researchers in human flourishing, earlier the authors have developed a framework containing psychological information important for flourishing of the target group of elderly persons.

Layer Cake – set up

Before the start of the exercise, we asked the four students in each design group to gather narratives from the target group, that is, personal stories containing psychological and experiential information from respectively four elderly persons. Since we aimed for coverage of the varied, heterogeneous group of elderly people, the four students were asked to each cover a resident residing in one of the following four types of elderly housing: (1) living independently at home, (2) residing with family members or living at home and receiving help, (3) residing in an assisted living initiative and (4) living in a residential care centre (RCC). The purpose was for the students to get a grip on the daily activities, life aspirations, hopes, and

fears of elderly people regarding their present and future.

In addition to the collected narratives, the authors provided the students with a framework called ‘the building blocks of elderly flourishing’ that was composed after a review of gerontology literature in four key journals in the field of aging research: *Journal of Aging Studies*, *Aging International*, *Archives of Gerontology and Geriatrics* and the *International Journal of Gerontology*. This literature review was conducted to upload each of the five items of the acronym and well-being-model P.E.R.M.A. (Seligman, 2011) with specifications regarding the target group of elderly persons (Stevens et al, 2016b). The building blocks of elderly flourishing contain specific psychological information, and explicate 17 important psychological needs of this target group that are important for their flourishing, see Table 1. We purposefully described the psychological information under the format of ‘strategies’ or generalist actions which elderly persons can undertake, in a way that it is understandable for architects and can be applied together with narratives in a design process focusing on designing meaningful activities.

Layer Cake – student’s design process

Students collected narratives from their target group via in-depth interviews. In addition, some gave the elderly person a diary to fill in, accompanied the interviewee on daily activities, etcetera. Coming to the design workshop with their collected narratives, we asked each design group to set up a think process in which they had to distil a main ‘generic’ social topic for their spatial layer in Layer Cake out of the narratives. Students first came up with for instance a library, a museum or a garden. The proposed functions are all closely linked to the traditional living habits of educating, entertaining, relaxing, etcetera. By using the real-life narrative information from the elderly population as the base to select a social topic, Layer Cake’s design and its affordances are a direct response

Table 1. The 17 building blocks of elderly flourishing, in five overarching themes.

Overarching theme	Building blocks
BEING ACTIVE – CHALLENGE YOURSELF	Train & master existing skills Execute hobbies Engage in meaningful activities Develop new skills -> challenge!
SOCIALLY ACTIVE IN A NETWORK	Solidarity & empathy Productive role in society Built & invest in social network
IDENTITY ENFORCING	Reminiscence Narratives Mindfulness & spirituality
BEING VISIBLE TO THE WORLD - COUNTING IN	Sharing knowledge, items, hobbies Volunteering & charity Organizational involvement: having a role in community
STAYING ENGAGED WITH LIFE – SELF- MAINTAINING	Resourcefulness – adaptation Exercise control Goals & individual choices Engagement with life

to actual concerns, hopes and wishes from this target group.

In the analysis of the gathered narratives, it became clear that respondents gave information in six categories: ‘ambitions for the future’, ‘activities that had to be given up’, ‘current hobbies’, ‘something that gives meaning’, ‘important objects’ and ‘favourite location’. The first four categories contain intangible, experiential information, the latter two contain tangible information with a spatial undertone. In the students’ processing of the data with the purpose of defining a generic social topic to design their social layer around, we noticed that they did not automatically search for the most frequently occurring activities, but often empathically chose for one interesting quote or a remarkable social activity an interviewee tried to maintain. For instance, in the project “Ex Libris” one interviewee living in a service flat mentioned she visits the adjoining RCC once a month to volunteer with a small book cart from the local library to accommodate RCC residents with books. She is also still active as a lector in her parish. Empathically, students were drawn to this anecdotal fact, and then searched their data for aspects that could be linked to the topic of reading. Eventually, they decided to further develop ‘library’ as their social topic. Another approach other students took was seeking for a ‘general truth’ in the data, a main topic that was present throughout all personal details and anecdotes. The ‘general truth’ behind the topic was distilled by students out of the different ways the interviewees handled or executed it. For instance in the project “Sport-o-rama”, students found that sports was a recurring topic, and their interviewees had different relations to a sport experience: ranging from watching sports on television, simulating sports on the x-box, actively practising sports, etcetera. Other student groups tried to distil experiences that provided meaning out of their data, for instance the design group of project “Jong geleerd oud gedaan”, noticed that their interviewees all valued getting together with family or friends, preferably in the cosiness of their own living room. Bringing the two together, led to their topic of a large public ‘living room’ equipped with homemade or second-life furniture.

After the processing of the narratives, we asked students to build further on their generic social topic, and include and interpret the *building blocks of elderly flourishing* we had given them. This moment formed the transition between component one ‘target group’ and component two ‘program’. In the next part, we will discuss in detail how students in cooperation with the first author developed methods to transform the generic social topic into a social concept and an enriched program to assist the target group in flourishing, with the use of the building blocks framework.

Component two Program: Designing an enriched program

Theory

In DfHF the designed activities must provide meaning for the target group; even the most banal activities can become meaningful if they are connected to and fulfil certain psychological needs of users (Desmet & Hassenzahl, 2012; Hassenzahl et al, 2013).

In transforming a generic social topic into a set of qualitative activities, in the viewpoint of the authors, the theory of narratives can be applied yet again, however in a different manner. Instead of the target group recalling life events and sharing life experiences, architects now have to create experiences and new 'memories', for instance via storytelling. Consequently, in architecture, inventing and writing out new narratives in the form of daily schedules, storyboards or usage patterns helps to enrich activities experientially. Since DfHF is based on fulfilling psychological needs, it is essential to find activities that can fulfil these needs. In other words, activities should incite specific behaviours in people. We believe that when designerly handling this, interesting links can be found with the theory on design for behaviour change (e.g. Fogg, 2009). We do not directly aim for behaviour change in DfHF, but the two have in common that they both aim to encourage people to undertake certain pre-designed activities, that incite an internal process; whether that process is behaviour change or flourishing. Fogg's model for design for behaviour change (2009) can be useful to include in designing activity patterns for flourishing; it demonstrates that intensity, frequency and duration are important aspects that activities need to be measured up to if the purpose is inducing positive internal change. These factors can assist designers in deepening the experience within their activities. In DfHF, we feel that all three factors are inherently linked to the natural differentiation within heterogeneous target groups such as 'elderly persons', differing in mental, physical and many other characteristics. Consequently, these users are in need of variations in intensity, frequency and duration within an activity to keep it interesting and successful to all.

Layer Cake – set up

Next to the insights borrowed from design for behaviour change and narrative theory, the framework of *building blocks of elderly flourishing* was used as input in Layer Cake's set up. The framework was inserted in the design process as a base to anticipate on specific behaviours and to start designing activity patterns. Concretely, it presented students the psychological needs and desired behaviours they had to fulfil. Narrative theory provided students with a method that stimulated thinking in terms of scenarios and activity patterns that provide users with a variety of 'chances' (activities) to fulfil their needs. The insights from design for behaviour change had the purpose of designing activities that speak to the entire target group, and respond to differentiation (e.g. physical and mental characteristics, age).

In that matter, the set up should stimulate students to enrich and add extra layers to the generic social topic they pinpointed in step one of the design exercise, in a way that it supports the target group in flourishing. Notwithstanding theoretical insights from other design branches are useful in architecture, we needed to search for a systematic way to combine knowledge and design so-called meaningful activities in architecture. Since this approach requests a new design attitude, the authors opted to co-work with students in finding ways to design these meaningful activities and desired behaviours. We gave students the remaining four days of design week 1 to transfer their social topic into an enriched program containing full-grown activity patterns.

Layer Cake – (researcher's &) student's design process

During this phase, students were asked to develop the experiential content of their spatial layer, with the help of the theoretical information we had provided them with.

During the first two days of designing social scenarios, we noticed that the role of the first author was important in order to co-work with students to develop methods to combine their chosen topic and the 'psychological information' of the building blocks into architectural designing. To start with, the first author stimulated students to think out narratives: social stories and logical activity patterns that could occur within their chosen social topic. Each time, examples were given in what way the building blocks could help students to come up with these scenarios, and stay focused on the target group's needs. For example, the design group working around the topic 'spending time outdoors' (project "Tussen de soep en de patatten") were stimulated to develop garden activities that allowed residents to pick up on their hobby of gardening (to fulfil building blocks 'execute hobbies' and 'train & master existing skills', and even 'mindfulness'), invent scenarios with cooking workshops that allowed residents to maintain or gain extra skills regarding preparing food (to fulfil building blocks 'train & master existing skills', 'develop new skills' and even 'engage in meaningful activities'), but could also lead to fulfilling building block 'reminiscence' when preparing long lost recipes and picking up on the aroma of home-made soup, or to fulfilment of 'volunteering and charity' and 'solidarity & empathy', when a sort of soup kitchen is established. During these first attempts of designing scenarios, it became clear that most of the design groups tried to 'manage' the design challenge by subcategorizing their chosen topic. For instance the group whose social topic was 'sports', made the subdivision of 'active', 'semi-active' and 'passive' ways of practising sports. The group whose social topic was 'spending time outdoors' even made two types of subdivisions: (1) activities in each of the four seasons and (2) three additional themes they further wanted to explore in their design: 'vegetable garden', 'soup bar' and 'relaxing outdoors'. This was an important first step in concretizing their topic and simultaneously linking it even more to the lifestyle of elderly persons, since the inspiration for categorization came from rereading the narratives that they collected at the

Figure 3. Flow of activities.

Figure 4. Spider web of activities.

start of the master class. After subcategorizing, it became easier for students to develop scenarios related to their social topic, and finding matches between the scenarios and the building blocks in the framework.

We call this step in the design process ‘concretizing social concept’, see Figure 6.

The next days, the first author encouraged students to elaborate the scenarios they had already designed, by (1) iteratively trying to include as many building blocks as possible in the story and expanding their designed new narratives, (2) exploring links between different scenarios, (3) finding ramifications in the scenario, meaning that one action might lead to a number of possible other actions, and (4) making sure that every type of elderly person is ‘included’ in the scenarios, by layering activities in intensity, duration and frequency (Fogg, 2009). At that moment, we noticed that students further developed the scenarios in two manners: starting out from the user (the different types of elderly persons (target group) and outsiders) or from the subthemes and categorizations within their social topic. For instance in the design project of the social topic ‘library’, the design group drew a flow chart per type of user that they had defined in their design process (i.e., a fit resident of Layer Cake, a resident with dementia disorder and the grandson of a resident), and developed a scenario that included many actions and activities with this user as a protagonist, and other people included. The building blocks were applied in this process to design activities that have a specific aimed effect on the predefined user(s). This approach led to the development of a *flow of activities*; one activity set others in motion, and an overlap between the scenarios arose. By repeating this process many times, and trying to fulfil as many building blocks as possible, a coherent story for the usage patterns of the library was developed and a logical sequence of activities and events was presented, see an example in Figure 3.

Most of the design groups started out from the subthemes they had developed for their social topic. For instance the group working with the topic ‘sports’ had come up with two types of subcategorizations: four different sport zones (yoga & dance, mini golf, running, and active sport such as biking) and three

different perspectives on and intensities of sports related to a specific user group (a resident’s kin, a resident that likes recreational sports, a resident in need of physical rehabilitation). In developing their scenarios, specifically for each of the four zones, they first filled in a framework of building blocks with suitable activities. Concretely, they ran through each of the 17 building blocks to define events that could be undertaken. Then, per zone, they coded their activities with regards to the three different types of user groups they had defined earlier. In that way, the activities became even more layered and detailed regarding the zone they were in, and the specifics and characteristics of the different user groups. That way of working led to a web of many different empowering events that can occur for all different users within the four zones. Also, by each designed addition, the activities became more socially layered and detailed in flourishing effect. So that way of designing led to an elaborate mix of activities, or in other words a spider web of activities within the imaginary boundaries of the social topic, as illustrated in Figure 4.

We labelled this step in the design process ‘scenario development, enriched program’, see Figure 6.

With the end of the first design week approaching, students were asked to continue and keep on elaborating the scenarios they had designed, by including more possible users, searching for more overlaps between the activities or including more building blocks within the story told. This became an iterative process of thinking out scenarios and immediately evaluating them by (re)running them through the framework of building blocks, with all the different members of the target group in mind. Each time another type of person entered a scenario, the framework was reapplied to argue what behaviour could be provoked and in what way that person could be assisted in flourishing in the already designed scenarios, or what new scenarios had to be written. Also, when non-residents (visitors, neighbours, passers-by) entered the scenarios, the framework was of use to see in what way these people could benefit each other and residents. Consequently, programs of usage became even more enriched and layered in flourishing experiences, and an overall picture of the daily goings in each spatial layer in Layer Cake became clear. Then, the socio-cultural affordances were designed, and the first part of a DfHF-process is ran through, see Figure 1.

Visualization

Throughout the first design week, students had to daily communicate their designed social scenarios to the first author and guest studio mentors. Hence, attention to finding suitable ways of visually communicating the complex social designs was on the students’ to do list as well.

When analysing students’ ways of representation at the jury that concluded the first design week, we noticed differences in visualisation methods used by the design groups that had designed their enriched program starting out from developed subcategories within their social topic, and the groups that had

Figure 5. Representations to communicate designed socio-cultural affordances.

started from the users. As the left part of Figure 5 demonstrates, a visual representation of the framework of building blocks, added with collages and 3D images per scenario was the most important output of design groups that had started out from their subcategories. Design groups that had started from the user mostly applied flow charts and puzzle pictures, see the right part of Figure 5.

Conclusion: programmatic writing as a method to design socio-cultural affordances in a DfHF-process

As a conclusion, in Figure 6, all of the described design steps thoroughly discussed in this paper are generalized into a timeline visualizing the design process of socio-cultural affordances. In the top part of the time line, per yellow dot, the design steps are explained. The black dotted arrows, explain what kind of information or tips were inserted in the design process and by whom.

We label this design method “programmatic writing”. Concretely, programmatic writing is a mix of consecutive steps a designer needs to run through in order to develop an *enriched program*, which is key in HF-architecture. An enriched program exists of activity patterns and scenarios that comply with the psychological needs of the target group. When executed, the activities will assist these persons in flourishing. Those activities concern what we have labelled the so-called “socio-cultural affordances” of space.

By consciously using the verb “writing” in the naming of our design method programmatic writing, we stress that we focus on intangible programmatic features that need to be ‘designed’ and need particular attention in the early design phase, whereby we need to take into account that traditional work approaches such as sketching and drawing are not directly applicable in the early steps of programmatic writing. The program for a target group has to literally be thought out, and written out to make it graspable. Only in the final steps of programmatic writing, the designed scenarios are to be visualized by drawn schemes or collages as presented in Figure 5. Even then, the visualizations are from a different order than the floor-plan-sketches or 3D-images an architect traditionally produces when designing (e.g. Pena, 2001; Cross, 2011). To conclude, in contrast to traditional design methods, there is a prolonged and very intense design time spent on the intangible aspects of

architecture, namely the program with its activities as socio-cultural affordances, instead of jumping rather quickly into actual spatial designs that contain tangible information such as form, structure and material information (Cross, 2011).

Now that the method of programmatic writing is discussed, we can insert these insights into the theoretical trajectory for DfHF. In Figure 7, we have repeated the theoretical trajectory, and uploaded the socio-cultural affordance-part with the details and techniques of the developed design method of programmatic writing. The process starts by collecting experiential and psychological information from the target group. A close contact and empathic connection with this target group is requested. Next, the design process continues with designing enriched social programs. Thinking out narratives (storytelling) and scenario writing are important techniques that architects can use to design meaningful activities out of the psychological data that are collected from their target group. We believe that designing these social scenarios on different architectural scale levels is a way of integrating very complex demands of heterogenic target groups in a manageable way. Scenarios can be combined, placed next to each other to find interesting overlaps, points of conflict or opportunities. Note that in order to DfHF, architects must still translate the socio-cultural affordances into physical affordances. In further research, we aim to theoretically and designerly explore methods to do so.

Discussion, implications & further research

In this paper we discussed the design method of “programmatic writing” that was developed during the design exercise Layer Cake, with the purpose of introducing it as a way to design socio-cultural affordances in a DfHF-process. It is a first attempt in transforming DfHF-theory into a practical tool to steer architects. The design exercise with students made clear that a mentality shift needs to occur during designing, since spatial designers have the intention to direct their attention towards sketching and drawing spatial ‘solutions’ (Pena, 2001; Cross, 2011). However in DfHF, intangible aspects need to be handled in detail before the actual spatial decisions can be made. Therefore, during the exercise, the first author stressed the importance of using the framework of the building blocks, thinking in terms of scenarios and telling stories to each other; and somewhat ‘forbid’ the students in the first design week to speak in spatial terms and jump to spatial

Figure 6. Design process of socio-cultural affordances: the method of programmatic writing.

Socio-cultural affordance:
Meaningful, rich experiences

Figure 7. Programmatic writing inserted in the theoretical trajectory to DfHF in architecture.

conclusions. On the other hand, 'spatial' expectations of the users need to be met when a design is presented to them. Therefore, in DfHF, architects must find suitable ways to concretize their designed socio-cultural affordances into a more 'tangible' way of presentation than simply verbal communication. This implies that designers need to experiment with communication tools of sketching and drawing to get the message across and convince with their designed efforts and the experiences the design will provide.

With programmatic writing as a possible design method to design socio-cultural affordances, an important step in concretizing this trajectory is set. This has implications for architectural practice, since designers are in need of explicit information on how to DfHF, and place the experiential world of the user first. However, more research is necessary to explore how this method can work in actual design practice and what possible pitfalls designers can encounter; truly getting to know the target group and investing design time in developing an enriched program prolongs the design process, which has financial consequences for firm and client, an issue that cannot be neglected in the context of professional design activities. Also, DfHF requests a mind-shift of the designer, so it is our responsibility to research in what way we can assist the designer to overcome difficulties in that matter, and develop the design tool in a way that it is easy to apply for designers, and presented to them in the visual language they are familiar with.

If the trajectory is found to be useful and applicable in practice, we believe it is relevant for many architectural contexts such as care typologies or school environments, in short, places where people need to reside for a specific period of time. If patients in care environments and children in school environments feel well and are flourishing, this might have a positive influence on their healing or study performance as well. Thereby we aim to reach a large number of the population. DfHF positively influences the psychological well-being of people, and we can thereby contribute to the Gross National Happiness of nations (The Centre for Bhutan Studies & GNH Research, 2015).

In future research, we will investigate in what way architecture with a more humane undertone implicitly works with the three components in the trajectory. Also, we aim to set up a similar research path to designerly explore physical affordances as well (see Figure 1), and by that complete a DfHF-trajectory for architects and interior architects from an affordance perspective. However, we believe that this new way of designing can be extrapolated to other design branches, such as industrial design, etcetera. Design methods will logically differ from the architectural ones, so more research is necessary in that respect.

References

Chemero, A. (2003). An Outline of a Theory of Affordance. *Ecological Psychology*, 15(2), 181-191.

Chemero, A. (2009). *Radical embodied cognitive science*. Cambridge, Massachusetts, London: MIT Press.

Cross, N. (2011). *Design thinking*. London: Springer.

Delle Fave, A., Brdar, I., Freire, T., Vella-Brodrick, D., & Wissing, M. P. (2011). The eudaimonic and hedonic components of happiness: Qualitative and quantitative findings. *Social Indicators Research*, 100(2), 185-207.

Desmet, P. M. A. & Hassenzahl, M. (2012). Towards happiness: Possibility-driven design. *Human-Computer Interaction: The Agency Perspective*, SCI 396, 3-27.

Desmet, P. M. A., & Pohlmeier, A. E. (2013). Positive design: An introduction to design for subjective well-being. *International Journal of Design*, 7(3), 5-19.

Fogg, B.J. (2009). *The behavior Grid: 35 ways behaviour can change*. Retrieved October 10 2015 from: <http://bjfogg.com/fbg.html>

Gerards, S. & De Bleckere S. (2014). Narrative Thinking in Architectural Education. In: D. Rockwood & M. Sarvimäki (Eds.), *Beyond Architecture: New Intersections & Connections ARCC/EAAE Architectural Research Conference Proceedings* (pp. 305-311). Hawaii; University of Hawaii.

Gibson, J. J. (1979). The theory of affordances. In *The ecological approach to visual perception*. Boston: Houghton Mifflin Company.

Hassenzahl, M., Eckoldt, K., Diefenbach, S., Laschke, M., Lenz, E., & Kim, J. (2013). Designing moments of meaning and pleasure. Experience design and happiness. *International Journal of Design*, 7(3), 21-31.

Havik, K. & Tielens, G. (2013). Atmosphere, compassion and embodied experience. A conversation about atmosphere with Juhani Pallasmaa. In K. Havik, G. Tielens & H. Teerds (Eds.), *Sfeerbouwen. Building Atmosphere* (pp. 33-52). Rotterdam: NAi010 Publishers.

Norman, D. A. (2002). *The Design of Everyday Things*. New York: Basic Books.

Oppliger, M. (2015). *Jan Gehl: "Architects know very little about people"* *TagesWoche*. Retrieved April 13 2015 from <http://www.tageswoche.ch/+fmm3q>

Parnell, R. (2003). Knowledge Skills and Arrogance: Educating for collaborative practice. In E. Harder (Ed.), *Writings in Architectural Education: EAAE Transaction on architectural education No 15*. Copenhagen. Leuven: EAAE.

Pena, W. (2001). *Problem seeking: an architectural programming primer* (4th edn). New York: John Wiley & Sons.

Rietveld, E. & Kiverstein, J. (2014). A rich landscape of affordances. *Ecological Psychology*, 26(4), 325-352.

Seligman, M.E.P. (2011). *Flourish*. New York: free Press.

Stevens, R., Petermans, A., Vanrie, J. (2014). Converting happiness theory into (interior) architectural design missions. Designing for subjective well-being in residential care centers. In: *Proceedings of the 6th Annual Architectural Research Symposium, Finland 2014: Designing and Planning the Built Environment for Human Well-Being*. Oulu: Oulu University.

Stevens, R., Petermans, A., Vanrie, J. (2016a). Design for human flourishing in architecture: designing spatial flourishing affordances. *Manuscript submitted*.

Stevens, R., Petermans, A., Vanrie, J. (2016b). Design for human flourishing: the building blocks of elderly flourishing. *Manuscript submitted*

The Centre for Bhutan Studies and NGH Research. (2015). *Gross National Happiness Studies*. Retrieved April 21 2016 from <http://www.grossnationalhappiness.com>

Till, J. (2005). Architecture and Participation. In P. Blundell Jones, D. Petrescu & J. Till (Eds.), *Architecture and Participation* (pp. 25-44). London: Routledge.

Warren, W.H. (1984). Perceiving affordances: Visual guidance of stair climbing. *Journal of Experimental Psychology: Human Perception and Performance*, 10, 683-703.